

Hotspots of soil pollution: glyphosate and aminomethylphosphonic acid risks to terrestrial ecosystems and human health – Dataset.

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Abstract: The high application of pesticides at a global scale for food production can lead to the occurrence and accumulation of chemicals such as one of the most used herbicides, glyphosate (GLY), and its main metabolite, aminomethylphosphonic acid (AMPA). A literature review was performed to determine worldwide occurrence, with 37 manuscripts selected. The maximum values of these chemicals on soil were used to generate a risk quotient (RQ), the incremental lifetime carcinogenic risk (ILCR) and the non-cancer risk (hazard index - HI). This manuscript presents the raw data extracted from the selected manuscripts and the data analysed for RQ, ILCR, and HI.

Keywords: Pesticides, Risk Quotient (RQ), Incremental Lifetime Carcinogenic Risk (ILCR), Non-cancer Risk (HI), Soil Pollution

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Specifications table

Subject	Soil Science and Biology
Specific subject area	Environmental Toxicology
Type of data	Tables and Charts
How the data were acquired	A Scopus literature review examined the global occurrence of the pesticides glyphosate (GLY) and aminomethylphosphonic acid (AMPA). Using the maximum recorded values, the risk quotients (RQ) for earthworms and springtails, as well as incremental lifetime cancer risk (ILCR) and hazard index (HI), following the EPA's Exposure Factors Handbook, were calculated. The resulting indexes and scores were newly calculated for different global regions.
Data format	Raw and Analysed
Description of data collection	This manuscript presents data collected from a literature review of 37 studies and data calculated based on the levels of pesticides glyphosate (GLY), aminomethylphosphonic acid (AMPA), and the previously mentioned parameters.
Data source location	<p>This manuscript uses data from the following manuscripts:</p> <p>L.L. Alonso, P.M. Demetrio, M. Agustina Etchegoyen, D.J. Marino, Glyphosate and atrazine in rainfall and soils in agroproductive areas of the pampas region in Argentina, <i>Science of the Total Environment</i> 645 (2018) 89-96. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2018.07.134</p> <p>V.C. Aparicio, S. Aimar, E. De Gerónimo, M.J. Mendez, J.L. Costa, Glyphosate and AMPA concentrations in wind-blown material under field conditions, <i>Land Degradation and Development</i> 29(5) (2018) 1317-1326. https://doi.org/10.1002/ldr.2920</p> <p>V.C. Aparicio, E. De Gerónimo, D. Marino, J. Primost, P. Carriquiriborde, J.L. Costa, Environmental fate of glyphosate and aminomethylphosphonic acid in surface waters and soil of agricultural basins, <i>Chemosphere</i> 93(9) (2013) 1866-1873. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemosphere.2013.06.041</p> <p>C.P.M. Bento, S. van der Hoeven, X. Yang, M.M.J.P.M. Riksen, H.G.J. Mol, C.J. Ritsema, V. Geissen, Dynamics of glyphosate and AMPA in the soil surface layer of glyphosate-resistant crop cultivations in the loess Pampas of Argentina, <i>Environmental Pollution</i> 244 (2019) 323-331. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envpol.2018.10.046</p> <p>C. Bernasconi, P.M. Demetrio, L.L. Alonso, T.M. Mac Loughlin, E. Cerdá, S.J. Sarandón, D.J. Marino, Evidence for soil pesticide contamination of an agroecological farm from a neighboring chemical-based production system, <i>Agriculture, Ecosystems and Environment</i> 313 (2021). https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2021.107341</p> <p>E. Börjesson, L. Torstensson, New methods for determination of glyphosate and (aminomethyl)phosphonic acid in water and soil, <i>Journal of Chromatography A</i> 886(1-2) (2000) 207-216. https://doi.org/10.1016/S0021-9673(00)00514-8</p> <p>A.M. Botero-Coy, M. Ibáñez, J.V. Sancho, F. Hernández, Improvements in the analytical methodology for the residue determination of the herbicide glyphosate in soils by liquid chromatography coupled to mass spectrometry, <i>Journal of Chromatography A</i> 1292 (2013) 132-141. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chroma.2012.12.007</p> <p>L. Carretta, A. Cardinali, A. Onofri, R. Masin, G. Zanin, Dynamics of Glyphosate and Aminomethylphosphonic Acid in Soil Under Conventional and Conservation Tillage, <i>International</i></p>

Journal of Environmental Research 15(6) (2021) 1037-1055. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s41742-021-00369-3>

K.A. da Silva, V.B. Nicola, R.T. Dudas, W.C. Demetrio, L.S. Maia, L. Cunha, M.L.C. Bartz, G.G. Brown, A. Pasini, P. Kille, N.G.C. Ferreira, C.M.R. de Oliveira, Pesticides in a case study on no-tillage farming systems and surrounding forest patches in Brazil, *Scientific Reports* 11(1) (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-021-88779-3>

T. Erban, M. Stehlik, B. Sopko, M. Markovic, M. Seifrtova, T. Halesova, P. Kovaricek, The different behaviors of glyphosate and AMPA in compost-amended soil, *Chemosphere* 207 (2018) 78-83. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemosphere.2018.05.004>

V. Geissen, V. Silva, E.H. Lwanga, N. Beriot, K. Oostindie, Z. Bin, E. Pyne, S. Busink, P. Zomer, H. Mol, C.J. Ritsema, Cocktails of pesticide residues in conventional and organic farming systems in Europe – Legacy of the past and turning point for the future, *Environmental Pollution* 278 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envpol.2021.116827>

S. Gunarathna, B. Gunawardana, M. Jayaweera, J. Manatunge, K. Zoysa, Glyphosate and AMPA of agricultural soil, surface water, groundwater and sediments in areas prevalent with chronic kidney disease of unknown etiology, Sri Lanka, *Journal of Environmental Science and Health - Part B Pesticides, Food Contaminants, and Agricultural Wastes* 53(11) (2018) 729-737. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03601234.2018.1480157>

M. Ibáñez, O.J. Pozo, J.V. Sancho, F.J. López, F. Hernández, Residue determination of glyphosate, glufosinate and aminomethylphosphonic acid in water and soil samples by liquid chromatography coupled to electrospray tandem mass spectrometry, *Journal of Chromatography A* 1081(2) (2005) 145-155. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chroma.2005.05.041>

X. Jing, W. Zhang, J. Xie, W. Wang, T. Lu, Q. Dong, H. Yang, Monitoring and risk assessment of pesticide residue in plant-soil-groundwater system about medlar planting in Golmud, *Environmental Science and Pollution Research* 28(21) (2021) 26413-26426. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11356-021-12403-0>

E. Karanasios, H. Karasali, A. Marousopoulou, A. Akrivou, E. Markellou, Monitoring of glyphosate and AMPA in soil samples from two olive cultivation areas in Greece: aspects related to spray operators activities, *Environmental Monitoring and Assessment* 190(6) <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10661-018-6728-x>

H. Karasali, G. Pavlidis, A. Marousopoulou, Investigation of the presence of glyphosate and its major metabolite AMPA in Greek soils, *Environmental Science and Pollution Research* 26(36) (2019) 36308-36321. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11356-019-06523-x>

P. Laitinen, K. Siimes, L. Eronen, S. Rämö, L. Welling, S. Oinonen, L. Mattsoff, M. Ruohonen-Lehto, Fate of the herbicides glyphosate, glufosinate-ammonium, phenmedipham, ethofumesate and metamitron in two Finnish arable soils, *Pest Management Science* 62(6) (2006) 473-491. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ps.1186>

L. Lupi, F. Bedmar, M. Puricelli, D. Marino, V.C. Aparicio, D. Wunderlin, K.S.B. Miglioranza, Glyphosate runoff and its occurrence in rainwater and subsurface soil in the nearby area of agricultural fields in Argentina, *Chemosphere* 225 (2019) 906-914. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemosphere.2019.03.090>

C.A. Mercado, A.G. Mactal, Degradation dynamics of glyphosate in two types of soil from corn fields of the Philippines, *International Journal of Agricultural Technology* 17(1) (2021) 185-192. ISSN 2630-0192 (Online)

M. Napoli, A.D. Marta, C.A. Zanchi, S. Orlandini, Transport of glyphosate and aminomethylphosphonic acid under two soil management practices in an Italian vineyard, *Journal of Environmental Quality* 45(5) (2016) 1713-1721 <https://doi.org/10.2134/jeq2016.02.0061>

- M. Newton, L.M. Horner, J.E. Cowell, D.E. White, E.C. Cole, Dissipation of Glyphosate and Aminomethylphosphonic Acid in North American Forests, *Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry* 42(8) (1994) 1795-1802. <https://doi.org/10.1021/jf00044a043>
- M. Newton, K.M. Howard, B.R. Kelsas, R. Danhaus, C. Marlene Lottman, S. Dubelman, Fate of Glyphosate in an Oregon Forest Ecosystem, *Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry* 32(5) (1984) 1144-1151. <https://doi.org/10.1021/jf00125a054>
- E. Okada, J.L. Costa, F. Bedmar, Adsorption and mobility of glyphosate in different soils under no-till and conventional tillage, *Geoderma* 263 (2016) 78-85. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoderma.2015.09.009>
- E. Okada, D. Pérez, E. De Gerónimo, V. Aparicio, H. Massone, J.L. Costa, Non-point source pollution of glyphosate and AMPA in a rural basin from the southeast Pampas, Argentina, *Environmental Science and Pollution Research* 25(15) (2018) 15120-15132. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11356-018-1734-7>
- C. Pelosi, C. Bertrand, V. Bretagnolle, M. Coeurdassier, O. Delhomme, M. Deschamps, S. Gaba, M. Millet, S. Nélieu, C. Fritsch, Glyphosate, AMPA and glufosinate in soils and earthworms in a French arable landscape, *Chemosphere* 301 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemosphere.2022.134672>
- D.J. Pérez, F.G. Iturburu, G. Calderon, L.A.E. Oyesqui, E. De Gerónimo, V.C. Aparicio, Ecological risk assessment of current-use pesticides and biocides in soils, sediments and surface water of a mixed land-use basin of the Pampas region, Argentina, *Chemosphere* 263 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemosphere.2020.128061>
- P.J. Peruzzo, A.A. Porta, A.E. Ronco, Levels of glyphosate in surface waters, sediments and soils associated with direct sowing soybean cultivation in north pampasic region of Argentina, *Environmental Pollution* 156(1) (2008) 61-66. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envpol.2008.01.015>
- J.E. Primost, D.J.G. Marino, V.C. Aparicio, J.L. Costa, P. Carriquiriborde, Glyphosate and AMPA, "pseudo-persistent" pollutants under real-world agricultural management practices in the Mesopotamic Pampas agroecosystem, Argentina, *Environmental Pollution* 229 (2017) 771-779. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envpol.2017.06.006>
- N.B. Ramirez Haberkon, S.B. Aimar, V.C. Aparicio, D.E. Buschiazzi, E. De Gerónimo, J.L. Costa, M.J. Mendez, Management effects on glyphosate and AMPA concentrations in the PM10 emitted by soils of the central semi-arid region of Argentina, *Aeolian Research* 49 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aeolia.2020.100658>
- N.B. Ramirez Haberkon, V.C. Aparicio, M.J. Mendez, First evidence of glyphosate and aminomethylphosphonic acid (AMPA) in the respirable dust (PM10) emitted from unpaved rural roads of Argentina, *Science of the Total Environment* 773 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2021.145055>
- É. Samson-Brais, M. Lucotte, M. Moingt, G. Tremblay, S. Paquet, Glyphosate and aminomethylphosphonic acid contents in field crops soils under various weed management practices, *Agrosystems, Geosciences and Environment* 5(3) (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1002/agg2.20273>
- V. Silva, L. Montanarella, A. Jones, O. Fernández-Ugalde, H.G.J. Mol, C.J. Ritsema, V. Geissen, Distribution of glyphosate and aminomethylphosphonic acid (AMPA) in agricultural topsoils of the European Union, *Science of the Total Environment* 621 (2018) 1352-1359. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2017.10.093>
- C.G. Soracco, R. Villarreal, L.A. Lozano, S. Vittori, E.M. Melani, D.J.G. Marino, Glyphosate dynamics in a soil under conventional and no-till systems during a soybean growing season, *Geoderma* 323 (2018) 13-21. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoderma.2018.02.041>

	<p>N. Tauchnitz, F. Kurzius, H. Rupp, G. Schmidt, B. Hauser, M. Schrödter, R. Meissner, Assessment of pesticide inputs into surface waters by agricultural and urban sources - A case study in the Querne/Weida catchment, central Germany, <i>Environmental Pollution</i> 267 (2020). https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envpol.2020.115186</p> <p>D. Tush, M.M. Maksimowicz, M.T. Meyer, Dissipation of polyoxyethylene tallow amine (POEA) and glyphosate in an agricultural field and their co-occurrence on streambed sediments, <i>Science of the Total Environment</i> 636 (2018) 212-219. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2018.04.246</p> <p>F. Veiga, J.M. Zapata, M.L. Fernandez Marcos, E. Alvarez, Dynamics of glyphosate and aminomethylphosphonic acid in a forest soil in Galicia, north-west Spain, <i>Science of the Total Environment</i> 271(1-3) (2001) 135-144. https://doi.org/10.1016/S0048-9697(00)00839-1</p> <p>M. Vlassa, M. Filip, V. Coman, V. Pănescu, C. Herghelegiu, S. Beldean-Galea, Glyphosate And Aminomethylphosphonic Acid Levels In Water And Soil Samples From Transylvanian Roma Community Analyzed By Hplc-Fld Method, <i>Studia Universitatis Babes-Bolyai Chemia</i> 67(4) (2022) 273-285. https://doi.org/10.24193/subbchem.2022.4.18</p>
Data accessibility	Data is available in this manuscript and Zenodo (http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14016717).
Related research article	N. G.C. Ferreira, K. A. da Silva, A. T. B. Guimarães, C. M. R. de Oliveira. Hotspots of soil pollution: possible glyphosate and aminomethylphosphonic acid risks on terrestrial ecosystems and human health, <i>Environment International</i> (2023) 108135. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envint.2023.108135

Value of the data

- Glyphosate (GLY), the world's most widely used herbicide, has been classified by the International Agency for Research on Cancer as potentially carcinogenic. The global levels of glyphosate (GLY), its primary breakdown product aminomethylphosphonic acid (AMPA), and their potential impact on ecosystems and human health are examined across different regions of the world.
- The collected data can aid other researchers conducting environmental and human risk assessments and monitoring by complementing their analyses.
- The data could aid other researchers in conducting further studies, such as modeling the distribution of GLY and AMPA, as well as assessing environmental and human health risks.

Objective

This manuscript provides a dataset that researchers can use to verify the results presented in the study of Ferreira et al. [15]. Policymakers can also access this dataset to evaluate GLY and AMPA levels in a specific geographic region and conduct environmental and public health risk assessments.

1. Data description

This manuscript presents a file named Metadata with six spreadsheets: i) Selected publications; ii) GLY and AMPA concentrations; iii) LC₅₀ and PNEC; iv) RQ GLY; v) RQ AMPA, vi) ILCR GLY; and vii) ILCR AMPA.

The 37 manuscripts used in the review study are presented in Table 1. As detailed in the "Experimental design, materials and methods" section, these references are numbered [1] to [37] and serve as the common link to the other tables. For each manuscript, the table shows the field, author names, title, published journal, year, issue, and page numbers. Except for reference [19], which includes the ISSN, all the other manuscripts list the corresponding digital object identifier (D.O.I.).

Table 1: Selected Publications - List of selected manuscripts used in this study.

Reference:	Publication Year:	Manuscript:	DOI:
[1]	2018	L.L. Alonso, P.M. Demetrio, M. Agustina Etchegoyen, D.J. Marino, Glyphosate and atrazine in rainfall and soils in agroproductive areas of the pampas region in Argentina, <i>Science of the Total Environment</i> 645 (2018) 89-96.	10.1016/j.scitotenv.2018.07.134
[2]	2018	V.C. Aparicio, S. Aimar, E. De Gerónimo, M.J. Mendez, J.L. Costa, Glyphosate and AMPA concentrations in wind-blown material under field conditions, <i>Land Degradation and Development</i> 29(5) (2018) 1317-1326.	10.1002/ldr.2920
[3]	2013	V.C. Aparicio, E. De Gerónimo, D. Marino, J. Primost, P. Carriquiriborde, J.L. Costa, Environmental fate of glyphosate and aminomethylphosphonic acid in surface waters and soil of agricultural basins, <i>Chemosphere</i> 93(9) (2013) 1866-1873.	10.1016/j.chemosphere.2013.06.041
[4]	2019	C.P.M. Bento, S. van der Hoeven, X. Yang, M.M.J.P.M. Riksen, H.G.J. Mol, C.J. Ritsema, V. Geissen, Dynamics of glyphosate and AMPA in the soil surface layer of glyphosate-resistant crop cultivations in the loess Pampas of Argentina, <i>Environmental Pollution</i> 244 (2019) 323-331.	10.1016/j.envpol.2018.10.046
[5]	2021	C. Bernasconi, P.M. Demetrio, L.L. Alonso, T.M. Mac Loughlin, E. Cerdá, S.J. Sarandón, D.J. Marino, Evidence for soil pesticide contamination of an agroecological farm from a neighboring chemical-based production system, <i>Agriculture, Ecosystems and Environment</i> 313 (2021).	10.1016/j.agee.2021.107341
[6]	2000	E. Börjesson, L. Torstensson, New methods for determination of glyphosate and (aminomethyl)phosphonic acid in water and soil, <i>Journal of Chromatography A</i> 886(1-2) (2000) 207-216.	10.1016/S0021-9673(00)00514-8
[7]	2013	A.M. Botero-Coy, M. Ibáñez, J.V. Sancho, F. Hernández, Improvements in the analytical methodology for the residue determination of the herbicide glyphosate in soils by liquid chromatography coupled to mass spectrometry, <i>Journal of Chromatography A</i> 1292 (2013) 132-141.	10.1016/j.chroma.2012.12.007
[8]	2021	L. Carretta, A. Cardinali, A. Onofri, R. Masin, G. Zanin, Dynamics of Glyphosate and Aminomethylphosphonic Acid in Soil Under Conventional and Conservation Tillage, <i>International Journal of Environmental Research</i> 15(6) (2021) 1037-1055.	10.1007/s41742-021-00369-3
[9]	2021	K.A. da Silva, V.B. Nicola, R.T. Dudas, W.C. Demetrio, L.S. Maia, L. Cunha, M.L.C. Bartz, G.G. Brown, A. Pasini, P. Kille, N.G.C. Ferreira, C.M.R. de Oliveira, Pesticides in a case study on no-tillage farming systems and surrounding forest patches in Brazil, <i>Scientific Reports</i> 11(1) (2021).	10.1038/s41598-021-88779-3
[10]	2018	T. Erban, M. Stehlik, B. Sopko, M. Markovic, M. Seifrtova, T. Halesova, P. Kovaricek, The different behaviors of glyphosate and AMPA in compost-amended soil, <i>Chemosphere</i> 207 (2018) 78-83.	10.1016/j.chemosphere.2018.05.004
[11]	2021	V. Geissen, V. Silva, E.H. Lwanga, N. Beriot, K. Oostindie, Z. Bin, E. Pyne, S. Busink, P. Zomer, H. Mol, C.J. Ritsema, Cocktails of pesticide residues in conventional and organic farming systems in Europe – Legacy of the past and turning point for the future, <i>Environmental Pollution</i> 278 (2021).	10.1016/j.envpol.2021.116827
[12]	2018	S. Gunarathna, B. Gunawardana, M. Jayaweera, J. Manatunge, K. Zoysa, Glyphosate and AMPA of agricultural soil, surface water, groundwater and sediments in areas prevalent with chronic kidney disease of unknown etiology, Sri Lanka, <i>Journal of Environmental Science and Health - Part B Pesticides, Food Contaminants, and Agricultural Wastes</i> 53(11) (2018) 729-737.	10.1080/03601234.2018.1480157
[13]	2005	M. Ibáñez, O.J. Pozo, J.V. Sancho, F.J. López, F. Hernández, Residue determination of glyphosate, glufosinate and aminomethylphosphonic acid in water and soil samples by liquid chromatography coupled to electrospray tandem mass spectrometry, <i>Journal of Chromatography A</i> 1081(2) (2005) 145-155.	10.1016/j.chroma.2005.05.041

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[14]	2021	X. Jing, W. Zhang, J. Xie, W. Wang, T. Lu, Q. Dong, H. Yang, Monitoring and risk assessment of pesticide residue in plant-soil-groundwater system about medlar planting in Golmud, Environmental Science and Pollution Research 28(21) (2021) 26413-26426.	10.1007/s11356-021-12403-0
[15]	2018	E. Karanasios, H. Karasali, A. Marousopoulou, A. Akrivou, E. Markellou, Monitoring of glyphosate and AMPA in soil samples from two olive cultivation areas in Greece: aspects related to spray operators activities, Environmental Monitoring and Assessment 190(6)	10.1007/s10661-018-6728-x
[16]	2019	H. Karasali, G. Pavlidis, A. Marousopoulou, Investigation of the presence of glyphosate and its major metabolite AMPA in Greek soils, Environmental Science and Pollution Research 26(36) (2019) 36308-36321.	10.1007/s11356-019-06523-x
[17]	2006	P. Laitinen, K. Siimes, L. Eronen, S. Rämö, L. Welling, S. Oinonen, L. Mattsoff, M. Ruohonen-Lehto, Fate of the herbicides glyphosate, glufosinate-ammonium, phenmedipham, ethofumesate and metamiltron in two Finnish arable soils, Pest Management Science 62(6) (2006) 473-491.	10.1002/ps.1186
[18]	2019	L. Lupi, F. Bedmar, M. Puricelli, D. Marino, V.C. Aparicio, D. Wunderlin, K.S.B. Miglioranza, Glyphosate runoff and its occurrence in rainwater and subsurface soil in the nearby area of agricultural fields in Argentina, Chemosphere 225 (2019) 906-914.	10.1016/j.chemosphere.2019.03.090
[19]	2021	C.A. Mercado, A.G. Mactal, Degradation dynamics of glyphosate in two types of soil from corn fields of the Philippines, International Journal of Agricultural Technology 17(1) (2021) 185-192.	ISSN 2630-0192 (Online)
[20]	2016	M. Napoli, A.D. Marta, C.A. Zanchi, S. Orlandini, Transport of glyphosate and aminomethylphosphonic acid under two soil management practices in an Italian vineyard, Journal of Environmental Quality 45(5) (2016) 1713-1721	10.2134/jeq2016.02.0061
[21]	1994	M. Newton, L.M. Horner, J.E. Cowell, D.E. White, E.C. Cole, Dissipation of Glyphosate and Aminomethylphosphonic Acid in North American Forests, Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry 42(8) (1994) 1795-1802.	10.1021/jf00044a043
[22]	1984	M. Newton, K.M. Howard, B.R. Kelpsas, R. Danhaus, C. Marlene Lottman, S. Dubelman, Fate of Glyphosate in an Oregon Forest Ecosystem, Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry 32(5) (1984) 1144-1151.	10.1021/jf00125a054
[23]	2016	E. Okada, J.L. Costa, F. Bedmar, Adsorption and mobility of glyphosate in different soils under no-till and conventional tillage, Geoderma 263 (2016) 78-85.	10.1016/j.geoderma.2015.09.009
[24]	2018	E. Okada, D. Pérez, E. De Gerónimo, V. Aparicio, H. Massone, J.L. Costa, Non-point source pollution of glyphosate and AMPA in a rural basin from the southeast Pampas, Argentina, Environmental Science and Pollution Research 25(15) (2018) 15120-15132.	10.1007/s11356-018-1734-7
[25]	2022	C. Pelosi, C. Bertrand, V. Bretagnolle, M. Coeurdassier, O. Delhomme, M. Deschamps, S. Gaba, M. Millet, S. Nélieu, C. Fritsch, Glyphosate, AMPA and glufosinate in soils and earthworms in a French arable landscape, Chemosphere 301 (2022).	10.1016/j.chemosphere.2022.134672
[26]	2021	D.J. Pérez, F.G. Iturburu, G. Calderon, L.A.E. Oyesqui, E. De Gerónimo, V.C. Aparicio, Ecological risk assessment of current-use pesticides and biocides in soils, sediments and surface water of a mixed land-use basin of the Pampas region, Argentina, Chemosphere 263 (2021).	10.1016/j.chemosphere.2020.128061

Reference:	Publication Year:	Manuscript:	DOI:
[27]	2008	P.J. Peruzzo, A.A. Porta, A.E. Ronco, Levels of glyphosate in surface waters, sediments and soils associated with direct sowing soybean cultivation in north pampasic region of Argentina, <i>Environmental Pollution</i> 156(1) (2008) 61-66.	10.1016/j.envpol.2008.01.015
[28]	2017	J.E. Primost, D.J.G. Marino, V.C. Aparicio, J.L. Costa, P. Carriquiriborde, Glyphosate and AMPA, "pseudo-persistent" pollutants under real-world agricultural management practices in the Mesopotamic Pampas agroecosystem, Argentina, <i>Environmental Pollution</i> 229 (2017) 771-779.	10.1016/j.envpol.2017.06.006
[29]	2021	N.B. Ramirez Haberkon, S.B. Aymar, V.C. Aparicio, D.E. Buschiazzo, E. De Gerónimo, J.L. Costa, M.J. Mendez, Management effects on glyphosate and AMPA concentrations in the PM10 emitted by soils of the central semi-arid region of Argentina, <i>Aeolian Research</i> 49 (2021).	10.1016/j.aeolia.2020.100658
[30]	2021	N.B. Ramirez Haberkon, V.C. Aparicio, M.J. Mendez, First evidence of glyphosate and aminomethylphosphonic acid (AMPA) in the respirable dust (PM10) emitted from unpaved rural roads of Argentina, <i>Science of the Total Environment</i> 773 (2021).	10.1016/j.scitotenv.2021.145055
[31]	2022	É. Samson-Brais, M. Lucotte, M. Moingt, G. Tremblay, S. Paquet, Glyphosate and aminomethylphosphonic acid contents in field crops soils under various weed management practices, <i>Agrosystems, Geosciences and Environment</i> 5(3) (2022).	10.1002/agg2.20273
[32]	2018	V. Silva, L. Montanarella, A. Jones, O. Fernández-Ugalde, H.G.J. Mol, C.J. Ritsema, V. Geissen, Distribution of glyphosate and aminomethylphosphonic acid (AMPA) in agricultural topsoils of the European Union, <i>Science of the Total Environment</i> 621 (2018) 1352-1359.	10.1016/j.scitotenv.2017.10.093
[33]	2018	C.G. Soracco, R. Villarreal, L.A. Lozano, S. Vittori, E.M. Melani, D.J.G. Marino, Glyphosate dynamics in a soil under conventional and no-till systems during a soybean growing season, <i>Geoderma</i> 323 (2018) 13-21.	10.1016/j.geoderma.2018.02.041
[34]	2020	N. Tauchnitz, F. Kurzius, H. Rupp, G. Schmidt, B. Hauser, M. Schrödter, R. Meissner, Assessment of pesticide inputs into surface waters by agricultural and urban sources - A case study in the Querne/Weida catchment, central Germany, <i>Environmental Pollution</i> 267 (2020).	10.1016/j.envpol.2020.115186
[35]	2018	D. Tush, M.M. Maksimowicz, M.T. Meyer, Dissipation of polyoxyethylene tallow amine (POEA) and glyphosate in an agricultural field and their co-occurrence on streambed sediments, <i>Science of the Total Environment</i> 636 (2018) 212-219.	10.1016/j.scitotenv.2018.04.246
[36]	2001	F. Veiga, J.M. Zapata, M.L. Fernandez Marcos, E. Alvarez, Dynamics of glyphosate and aminomethylphosphonic acid in a forest soil in Galicia, north-west Spain, <i>Science of the Total Environment</i> 271(1-3) (2001) 135-144.	10.1016/S0048-9697(00)00839-1
[37]	2022	M. Vlassa, M. Filip, V. Coman, V. Pănescu, C. Herghelegiu, S. Beldean-Galea, Glyphosate And Aminomethylphosphonic Acid Levels In Water And Soil Samples From Transylvanian Roma Community Analyzed By Hplc-Fld Method, <i>Studia Universitatis Babes-Bolyai Chemia</i> 67(4) (2022) 273-285.	10.24193/subbchem.2022.4.18

Table 2 presents the maximum concentrations of glyphosate (GLY) and aminomethylphosphonic acid (AMPA) found in the references listed in Table 10. The continent and country where the study was performed are also provided for each reference.

Highlighted cells indicate the limit of detection (LOD) or limit of quantification (LOQ) values, as described in the Notes. If AMPA data is unavailable, "N.D." is shown with the note "AMPA values not available".

For studies [18] and [20], the concentrations presented are based on average values, as maximum concentrations were not reported in the original manuscripts.

Table 2: GLY and AMPA concentrations - Maximum concentrations of GLY and AMPA were found in the references in different locations.

Reference:	Continent:	Country:	GLY (mg/kg)	AMPA (mg/kg)	Notes:
[1]	South America	Argentina	0.248	0.002	Highlighted cell: LOD value
[1]	South America	Argentina	0.233	0.732	
[1]	South America	Argentina	0.323	0.002	Highlighted cell: LOD value
[2]	South America	Argentina	0.0024	0.0063	
[2]	South America	Argentina	0.0095	0.0662	
[2]	South America	Argentina	0.1315	0.7035	
[3]	South America	Argentina	1.5023	2.256	
[4]	South America	Argentina	0.42	1.7	
[5]	South America	Argentina	1.26892	2.91917	
[6]	Europe	Sweden	2.7	0.382	
[6]	South America	Colombia	3.82	2.07	
[7]	South America	Argentina	0.67	1.19	
[8]	Europe	Italy	0.045	0.094	
[9]	South America	Brazil	66.38	26.03	
[10]	Europe	Czech	0.0118	0.067	
[10]	Europe	Portugal	7.843	4.294	
[10]	Europe	Netherlands	1.3	0.528	
[11]	Europe	Spain	0.18	1.626	
[12]	Asia	Sri Lanka	0.69	0.008	
[13]	Europe	Spain	0.73	5.61	
[14]	Asia	China	1.27	N.D.	AMPA values not available
[14]	Europe	Greece	0.023	0.027	
[15]	Europe	Greece	0.07	0.17	
[16]	Europe	Greece	40.6	2.5	
[17]	Europe	Finland	0.14	0.12	
[18]	South America	Argentina	0.132	0.3618	The average value was used since it not presented the maximum value
[19]	Asia	Philippines	0.01	0.01	Highlighted cell: LOD value
[20]	Europe	Italy	0.01	0.0655	The average value was used since it not presented the maximum value
[20]	North America	USA	1.96	0.06	
[20]	North America	USA	0.36	0.05	Highlighted cell: LOD value
[21]	North America	USA	0.05	0.05	Highlighted cell: LOD value

Reference:	Continent:	Country:	GLY (mg/kg)	AMPA (mg/kg)	Notes:
[22]	North America	USA	3.05	N.D.	AMPA values not available
[22]	South America	Argentina	0.01	0.3205	Highlighted cell: LOQ value
[22]	South America	Argentina	0.01	0.1275	
[23]	South America	Argentina	0.01	0.1609	
[24]	South America	Argentina	1.224	7.345	
[25]	Europe	France	0.598	0.135	
[26]	South America	Argentina	0.176	0.7125	
[27]	South America	Argentina	2.45	N.D.	AMPA values not available
[28]	South America	Argentina	8.105	38.939	
[29]	South America	Argentina	0.154	2.052	
[30]	South America	Argentina	0.177	1.485	
[31]	North America	Canada	0.01	0.2	Highlighted cell: LOD value
[31]	Europe	U.K.	0.21	0.59	
[31]	Europe	Denmark	0.34	0.61	
[31]	Europe	Portugal	2.05	1.92	
[31]	Europe	Italy	0.18	1.38	
[31]	Europe	Greece	0.63	0.38	
[31]	Europe	Spain	0.95	0.27	
[31]	Europe	Hungary	0.57	0.73	
[31]	Europe	Poland	0.23	0.42	
[31]	Europe	Netherlands	0.59	1.03	
[31]	Europe	France	0.27	0.78	
[32]	Europe	Germany	0.24	0.54	
[33]	South America	Argentina	0.06171	0.89599	
[34]	Europe	Germany	0.19	0.17	
[35]	North America	USA	0.018	0.11	
[36]	Europe	Spain	6.9	N.D.	AMPA values not available
[37]	Europe	Romenia	0.045925	N.D.	AMPA values not available
Maximum:			66.38	38.939	
Minimum:			0.0024	0.002	

Table 3 presents the lethal concentration for 50% (LC₅₀) and predicted no-effect environmental concentration (PNEC) values for glyphosate (GLY) and its metabolite AMPA. The LC₅₀ represents the concentration of GLY in soil required to kill 50% of test organisms during a predetermined observation period. The PNEC values were calculated as described in the "Experimental design, materials and methods" section.

Table 3: LC₅₀ and PNEC - Lethal concentration 50 (LC₅₀) of GLY, along with the predicted no-effect environmental concentration (PNEC) values for GLY and AMPA. * OECD (1984) and OECD (2004); ** Natural fields sampled. LC50: concentration that causes 50% mortality in the test organism; PNEC: predicted no effect concentration estimated for GLY and AMPA.

Group	Test organism	Test duration (days)	Exposure type	LC ₅₀ (mg/kg)	PNEC (GLY)	PNEC (AMPA)	Reference:
Annelida	<i>Aporrectodea caliginosa</i>						
	<i>ssp. Trapezoides</i>	Chronic (37)	Natural Soil**	177.00	3.54	70.80	Mohamed et al. [1]
	<i>Esenia fetida</i>	Acute (14)	Artificial Soil*	327.80	6.56	131.12	Wang et al. [2]
	<i>Eisenia andrei</i>	Acute (3)	Filter Paper*	66.00	1.32	26.40	Piola et al. [3]
Collembola	<i>Folsomia candida</i>	Chronic (28)	Natural Soil**	1.13	0.02	0.45	Santos et al. [4]

Table 4 presents the risk quotient (RQ) values for glyphosate (GLY) across different species of earthworms and springtails, as referenced in Table 1. The individual and average RQ scores and the associated ecological risk assessment are provided for the earthworm species (*Aporrectodea caliginosa* ssp., *Trapezoides*, *Eisenia fetida*, and *Eisenia andrei*). The table also includes the RQ score and ecological risk for the springtail species *Folsomia candida*.

The next two columns display the RQ (Risk Quotient) scores for the springtail *Folsomia candida*, followed by the corresponding ecological risk levels. The table uses a colour-coded scheme to indicate the different risk categories:

- Green cells: Low ecological risk (RQ < 0.1),
- Yellow cells: Moderate ecological risk (0.1 < RQ < 1.0),
- Red cells: High ecological risk (RQ > 1.0).

Section 2, "Experimental design, materials and methods," outlines the formulas used to calculate RQ scores.

Table 4: RQ GLY - Risk quotient (RQ) of GLY for the different species of earthworms and springtails, along with the corresponding ecological risk. Green cells denote Low ecological risk (RQ < 0.1); Yellow cells denote Moderate ecological risk (0.1 < RQ < 1.0); and Red cells denote High ecological risk (RQ > 1.0).

Reference:	<i>A. caliginosa</i>	<i>E. fetida</i>	<i>E. andrei</i>	Average RQ (Annelida)	RQ (Annelida)	<i>F. candida</i>	RQ (Collembola):
[1]	0.070056	0.037828	0.187879	0.098588	Low	10.973451	High
[1]	0.065819	0.035540	0.176515	0.092625	Low	10.309735	High
[1]	0.091243	0.049268	0.244697	0.128403	Moderate	14.292035	High
[2]	0.000678	0.000366	0.001818	0.000954	Low	0.106195	Moderate
[2]	0.002684	0.001449	0.007197	0.003777	Low	0.420354	Moderate
[2]	0.037147	0.020058	0.099621	0.052275	Low	5.818584	High
[3]	0.424379	0.229149	1.138106	0.597211	Moderate	66.473451	High
[4]	0.118644	0.064063	0.318182	0.166963	Moderate	18.584071	High

Reference:	<i>A. caliginosa</i>	<i>E. fetida</i>	<i>E. andrei</i>	Average RQ (Annelida)	RQ (Annelida)	<i>F. candida</i>	RQ (Collembola):
[5]	0.358452	0.193551	0.961303	0.504435	Moderate	56.146903	High
[6]	0.762712	0.411836	2.045455	1.073334	High	119.469027	High
[6]	1.079096	0.582672	2.893939	1.518569	High	169.026549	High
[7]	0.189266	0.102196	0.507576	0.266346	Moderate	29.646018	High
[8]	0.012712	0.006864	0.034091	0.017889	Low	1.991150	High
[9]	18.751412	10.125076	50.287879	26.388122	High	2937.168142	High
[10]	0.003333	0.001800	0.008939	0.004691	Low	0.522124	Moderate
[10]	2.215537	1.196309	5.941667	3.117837	High	347.035398	High
[10]	0.367232	0.198292	0.984848	0.516791	Moderate	57.522124	High
[11]	0.050847	0.027456	0.136364	0.071556	Low	7.964602	High
[12]	0.194915	0.105247	0.522727	0.274297	Moderate	30.530973	High
[13]	0.206215	0.111348	0.553030	0.290198	Moderate	32.300885	High
[14]	0.358757	0.193716	0.962121	0.504865	Moderate	56.194690	High
[14]	0.006497	0.003508	0.017424	0.009143	Low	1.017699	High
[15]	0.019774	0.010677	0.053030	0.027827	Low	3.097345	High
[16]	11.468927	6.192800	30.757576	16.139768	High	1796.460177	High
[17]	0.039548	0.021354	0.106061	0.055654	Low	6.194690	High
[18]	0.037288	0.020134	0.100000	0.052474	Low	5.840708	High
[19]	0.002825	0.001525	0.007576	0.003975	Low	0.442478	Moderate
[20]	0.002825	0.001525	0.007576	0.003975	Low	0.442478	Moderate
[20]	0.553672	0.298963	1.484848	0.779161	Moderate	86.725664	High
[20]	0.101695	0.054912	0.272727	0.143111	Moderate	15.929204	High
[21]	0.014124	0.007627	0.037879	0.019877	Low	2.212389	High
[22]	0.861582	0.465223	2.310606	1.212470	High	134.955752	High
[22]	0.002825	0.001525	0.007576	0.003975	Low	0.442478	Moderate
[22]	0.002825	0.001525	0.007576	0.003975	Low	0.442478	Moderate
[23]	0.002825	0.001525	0.007576	0.003975	Low	0.442478	Moderate
[24]	0.345763	0.186699	0.927273	0.486578	Moderate	54.159292	High
[25]	0.168927	0.091214	0.453030	0.237724	Moderate	26.460177	High
[26]	0.049718	0.026846	0.133333	0.069965	Low	7.787611	High
[27]	0.692090	0.373703	1.856061	0.973951	Moderate	108.407080	High
[28]	2.289548	1.236272	6.140152	3.221991	High	358.628319	High
[29]	0.043503	0.023490	0.116667	0.061220	Low	6.814159	High
[30]	0.050000	0.026998	0.134091	0.070363	Low	7.831858	High
[31]	0.002825	0.001525	0.007576	0.003975	Low	0.442478	Moderate
[31]	0.059322	0.032032	0.159091	0.083482	Low	9.292035	High
[31]	0.096045	0.051861	0.257576	0.135161	Moderate	15.044248	High
[31]	0.579096	0.312691	1.553030	0.814939	Moderate	90.707965	High
[31]	0.050847	0.027456	0.136364	0.071556	Low	7.964602	High
[31]	0.177966	0.096095	0.477273	0.250445	Moderate	27.876106	High
[31]	0.268362	0.144905	0.719697	0.377655	Moderate	42.035398	High

Reference:	<i>A. caliginosa</i>	<i>E. fetida</i>	<i>E. andrei</i>	Average RQ (Annelida)	RQ (Annelida)	<i>F. candida</i>	RQ (Collembola):
[31]	0.161017	0.086943	0.431818	0.226593	Moderate	25.221239	High
[31]	0.064972	0.035082	0.174242	0.091432	Low	10.176991	High
[31]	0.166667	0.089994	0.446970	0.234543	Moderate	26.106195	High
[31]	0.076271	0.041184	0.204545	0.107333	Moderate	11.946903	High
[32]	0.067797	0.036608	0.181818	0.095407	Low	10.619469	High
[33]	0.017432	0.009413	0.046750	0.024532	Low	2.730531	High
[34]	0.053672	0.028981	0.143939	0.075531	Low	8.407080	High
[35]	0.005085	0.002746	0.013636	0.007156	Low	0.796460	Moderate
[36]	1.949153	1.052471	5.227273	2.742965	High	305.309735	High
[37]	0.012973	0.007005	0.034792	0.018257	Low	2.032080	High

Table 5 presents the risk quotient (RQ) values for aminomethylphosphonic acid (AMPA) across different species of earthworms and springtails, as referenced in Table 1. The individual and average RQ scores and the associated ecological risk assessment are provided for the earthworm species (*Aporrectodea caliginosa* ssp., *Trapezoides*, *Eisenia fetida*, and *Eisenia andrei*). The table also includes the RQ score and ecological risk for the springtail species *Folsomia candida*.

The next two columns display the RQ (Risk Quotient) scores for the springtail *Folsomia candida*, followed by the corresponding ecological risk levels. The table uses a colour-coded scheme to indicate the different risk categories:

- Green cells: Low ecological risk (RQ < 0.1),
- Yellow cells: Moderate ecological risk (0.1 < RQ < 1.0),
- Red cells: High ecological risk (RQ > 1.0).

Section 2, "Experimental design, materials and methods," outlines the formulas used to calculate RQ scores.

Table 5: RQ AMPA - Risk quotient (RQ) of AMPA for the different species of earthworms and springtails, along with the corresponding ecological risk. Green cells denote Low ecological risk (RQ < 0.1); Yellow cells denote Moderate ecological risk (0.1 < RQ < 1.0); and Red cells denote High ecological risk (RQ > 1.0).

Reference:	<i>A. caliginosa</i>	<i>E. fetida</i>	<i>E. andrei</i>	Average RQ (Annelida)	RQ (Annelida)	<i>F. candida</i>	RQ (Collembola):
[1]	0.000028	0.000015	0.000076	0.000040	Low	0.004425	Low
[1]	0.010339	0.005583	0.027727	0.014550	Low	1.619469	High
[1]	0.000028	0.000015	0.000076	0.000040	Low	0.004425	Low
[2]	0.000089	0.000048	0.000239	0.000125	Low	0.013938	Low
[2]	0.000935	0.000505	0.002508	0.001316	Low	0.146460	Moderate
[2]	0.009936	0.005365	0.026648	0.013983	Low	1.556416	High
[3]	0.031864	0.017206	0.085455	0.044842	Low	4.991150	High
[4]	0.024011	0.012965	0.064394	0.033790	Low	3.761062	High
[5]	0.041231	0.022263	0.110575	0.058023	Low	6.458341	High
[6]	0.005395	0.002913	0.014470	0.007593	Low	0.845133	Moderate
[6]	0.029237	0.015787	0.078409	0.041144	Low	4.579646	High
[7]	0.016808	0.009076	0.045076	0.023653	Low	2.632743	High

Reference:	<i>A. caliginosa</i>	<i>E. fetida</i>	<i>E.andrei</i>	Average RQ (Annelida)	RQ (Annelida)	<i>F. candida</i>	RQ (Collembola):
[8]	0.001328	0.000717	0.003561	0.001868	Low	0.207965	Moderate
[9]	0.367655	0.198520	0.985985	0.517387	Moderate	57.588496	High
[10]	0.000946	0.000511	0.002538	0.001332	Low	0.148230	Moderate
[10]	0.060650	0.032749	0.162652	0.085350	Low	9.500000	High
[10]	0.007458	0.004027	0.020000	0.010495	Low	1.168142	High
[11]	0.022966	0.012401	0.061591	0.032319	Low	3.597345	High
[12]	0.000113	0.000061	0.000303	0.000159	Low	0.017699	Low
[13]	0.079237	0.042785	0.212500	0.111508	Moderate	12.411504	High
[14]	N.D	N.D	N.D	N.D	N.D	N.D	N.D
[14]	0.000381	0.000206	0.001023	0.000537	Low	0.059735	Low
[15]	0.002401	0.001297	0.006439	0.003379	Low	0.376106	Moderate
[16]	0.035311	0.019067	0.094697	0.049691	Low	5.530973	High
[17]	0.001695	0.000915	0.004545	0.002385	Low	0.265487	Moderate
[18]	0.005110	0.002759	0.013705	0.007191	Low	0.800442	Moderate
[19]	0.000141	0.000076	0.000379	0.000199	Low	0.022124	Low
[20]	0.000925	0.000500	0.002481	0.001302	Low	0.144912	Moderate
[20]	0.000847	0.000458	0.002273	0.001193	Low	0.132743	Moderate
[20]	0.000706	0.000381	0.001894	0.000994	Low	0.110619	Moderate
[21]	0.000706	0.000381	0.001894	0.000994	Low	0.110619	Moderate
[22]	N.D	N.D	N.D	N.D	N.D	N.D	N.D
[22]	0.004527	0.002444	0.012140	0.006370	Low	0.709071	Moderate
[22]	0.001801	0.000972	0.004830	0.002534	Low	0.282080	Moderate
[23]	0.002273	0.001227	0.006095	0.003198	Low	0.355973	Moderate
[24]	0.103743	0.056017	0.278220	0.145993	Moderate	16.250000	High
[25]	0.001907	0.001030	0.005114	0.002683	Low	0.298673	Moderate
[26]	0.010064	0.005434	0.026989	0.014162	Low	1.576327	High
[27]	N.D	N.D	N.D	N.D	N.D	N.D	N.D
[28]	0.549986	0.296972	1.474962	0.773973	Moderate	86.148230	High
[29]	0.028983	0.015650	0.077727	0.040787	Low	4.539823	High
[30]	0.020975	0.011326	0.056250	0.029517	Low	3.285398	High
[31]	0.002825	0.001525	0.007576	0.003975	Low	0.442478	Moderate
[31]	0.008333	0.004500	0.022348	0.011727	Low	1.305310	High
[31]	0.008616	0.004652	0.023106	0.012125	Low	1.349558	High
[31]	0.027119	0.014643	0.072727	0.038163	Low	4.247788	High
[31]	0.019492	0.010525	0.052273	0.027430	Low	3.053097	High
[31]	0.005367	0.002898	0.014394	0.007553	Low	0.840708	Moderate
[31]	0.003814	0.002059	0.010227	0.005367	Low	0.597345	Moderate
[31]	0.010311	0.005567	0.027652	0.014510	Low	1.615044	High
[31]	0.005932	0.003203	0.015909	0.008348	Low	0.929204	Moderate
[31]	0.014548	0.007855	0.039015	0.020473	Low	2.278761	High
[31]	0.011017	0.005949	0.029545	0.015504	Low	1.725664	High

Reference:	<i>A. caliginosa</i>	<i>E. fetida</i>	<i>E.andrei</i>	Average RQ (Annelida)	RQ (Annelida)	<i>F. candida</i>	RQ (Collembola):
[32]	0.007627	0.004118	0.020455	0.010733	Low	1.194690	High
[33]	0.012655	0.006833	0.033939	0.017809	Low	1.982279	High
[34]	0.002401	0.001297	0.006439	0.003379	Low	0.376106	Moderate
[35]	0.001554	0.000839	0.004167	0.002186	Low	0.243363	Moderate
[36]	N.D	N.D	N.D	N.D	N.D	N.D	N.D
[37]	N.D	N.D	N.D	N.D	N.D	N.D	N.D

Table 6 outlines the parameters used to calculate the incremental lifetime carcinogenic risk (ILCR) and the non-cancer hazard index (HI) for the chemicals GLY and AMPA. For each parameter, the table provides the acronym, unit, value for different global regions, and the corresponding reference. In some cases, the formula to calculate the parameter is also included.

Table 6: ILCR and HI Parameters - Parameters used to estimate the risk to human health. Physiological and behavioural data related to the human lifestyle.

Parameter:	Acronym:	Unit:	Value				Reference / Notes
			Asia	Europe	North America	South America	
Soil ingestion rate	IRsoil	mg/day	33				EPA [5] - Value for moderate soil plus dust ingestion (pag.16)
Exposure duration	ED	year	72.88	79.23	77.81	74.06	WorldData [6] - Average life expectancy for men and women of the specific region
Exposure frequency	EF	day/year	252				Qu et al. [7]
Conversion factor	CF	kg/mg	1 x 10 ⁻⁰⁶				Qu et al. [7]
Bodyweight	BW	kg	66.83	77.61	83.4	74.3	WorldData [8] - Average body weight for men and women of the specific region
Average life span	AT	day	26600.11	28918.95	28400.65	27031.9	Formula: ED x 365
Bioconcentration factor	BCF	unitless	2.04 (GLY) or 2.38 (AMPA)				EPA [9] for GLY and EPA [10] for AMPA
Vegetable ingestion rate	IRveget	kg/day	0.501	0.297	0.25	0.146	FAO [11] - Average vegetable consumption of the specific region
Air inhalation rate	IRair	m3/day	13.068	12.946	12.965	13.046	EPA [5] - Based on the air inhalation rates until the maximum life expectancy of the specific region
Particle emission factor	PEF	m3/kg	1360000000				Qu et al. [7]
Surface area of the skin that contacts soil	SA	cm2/day	6280				EPA [5] - Sum of the most probable exposure routes: head, arms, hands, legs and feet
Dermal surface factor	DAF	mg/m2	0.2				Qu et al. [7]
Dermal absorption factor	ABS	unitless	0.13				ORS [12]
Oral slope factor	SFo	mg/kg/day	6.162 x 10 ⁻⁰⁴	6.397 x 10 ⁻⁰⁴	6.513 x 10 ⁻⁰⁴	6.3279 x 10 ⁻⁰⁴	Formula: 0.0000897 x (BW/0.03) ^{1/4} Based on OEHHA [13]
Fraction absorbed in gastrointestinal tract	ABSgi	unitless	1				ATSDR [14]
Dermal slope factor	SFabs	mg/kg/day	6.162 x 10 ⁻⁰⁴	6.397 x 10 ⁻⁰⁴	6.513 x 10 ⁻⁰⁴	6.3279 x 10 ⁻⁰⁴	Formula: SFo x ABSgi
Inhalation unit risk	IUR	mg/m3	0				Minimal risk levels (MRLs) at very high concentrations. ATSRD [14]
Oral dose reference	RfDo	mg/kg/day	0.1				EPA [9]
Dermal reference dose	RfDabs	mg/kg/day	0.1				Formula: RfDo x ABSgi
Inhalation reference concentration	RfCi	mg/m3	0				See IUR

Table 7 presents the incremental lifetime carcinogenic risk (ILCR) and the non-cancer hazard index (HI) for the different exposure routes (ADD_i): soil ingestion (ADD_{soil}), food ingestion (ADD_{food}), dermal contact (ADD_{derm}), and dust inhalation (ADD_{inh}); the correspondent slope factors (SF_i): oral slope factor (SF_{soil} and SF_{food}), dermal slope factor of dermal contact (SF_{abs}), and the inhalation unit risk (IUR), along with the reference dose for ingestion (RfD_o), and dermal contact (RfD_{abs}). The incremental lifetime carcinogenic risk (ILCR) and the non-cancer risk (hazard index - HI) are coloured according to the following parameters:

ILCR:

- Green cells indicate the risk to the human population to be acceptable ($ILCR < 1 \times 10^{-06}$),
- Yellow cells indicate some risk to the human population, with regulators being called to lower the risk with effective measures ($1 \times 10^{-06} < ILCR < 1 \times 10^{-4}$),
- Red cells indicate the high-risk probability of developing cancer over a lifetime ($ILCR > 1 \times 10^{-4}$).

HI:

- Green cells – considers that non-cancer health effects are not expected ($HI < 1$)
- Red cells – considers that non-cancer health effects are possible but not certain ($HI > 1$)

The equations and parameter ranges are presented in Section 2, which covers the experimental design, materials, and methods.

Table 7: ILCR and HI GLY - Incremental lifetime carcinogenic risk (ILCR) and hazard index (HI) calculated for GLY from different world regions (Asia, Europe, North and South America) for human health from the average daily dose by four exposure routes: soil intake, food intake, dermal contact, and inhalation.

Reference:	Continent:	Country:	ADD _{soil}	ADD _{food}	ADD _{derm}	ADD _{inh}	S _{Fo} (soil)	S _{Fo} (food)	S _{Fo} (derm)	IUR	ILCR	ADD _i	RfD _o	RfD _{abs}	HI
[12]	Asia	Sri Lanka	2.35E-07	7.28E-03	1.16E-06	6.85E-11	1.45E-10	4.49E-06	7.17E-10	0.00E+00	4.49E-06	7.28E-03	7.28E-02	7.28E-02	1.46E-01
[14]	Asia	China	4.33E-07	1.34E-02	2.14E-06	1.26E-10	2.67E-10	8.26E-06	1.32E-09	0.00E+00	8.26E-06	1.34E-02	1.34E-01	1.34E-01	2.68E-01
[19]	Asia	Philippines	3.41E-09	1.06E-04	1.69E-08	9.93E-13	2.10E-12	6.50E-08	1.04E-11	0.00E+00	6.50E-08	1.06E-04	1.06E-03	1.06E-03	2.11E-03
[6]	Europe	Sweden	7.93E-07	1.45E-02	3.92E-06	2.29E-10	5.07E-10	9.30E-06	2.51E-09	0.00E+00	9.30E-06	1.45E-02	1.45E-01	1.45E-01	2.91E-01
[8]	Europe	Italy	1.32E-08	2.42E-04	6.54E-08	3.81E-12	8.45E-12	1.55E-07	4.18E-11	0.00E+00	1.55E-07	2.42E-04	2.42E-03	2.42E-03	4.85E-03
[10]	Europe	Czech	3.46E-09	6.35E-05	1.71E-08	9.99E-13	2.22E-12	4.06E-08	1.10E-11	0.00E+00	4.06E-08	6.35E-05	6.35E-04	6.35E-04	1.27E-03
[11]	Europe	Portugal	2.30E-06	4.22E-02	1.14E-05	6.64E-10	1.47E-09	2.70E-05	7.29E-09	0.00E+00	2.70E-05	4.22E-02	4.22E-01	4.22E-01	8.44E-01
[11]	Europe	Netherlands	3.82E-07	7.00E-03	1.89E-06	1.10E-10	2.44E-10	4.48E-06	1.21E-09	0.00E+00	4.48E-06	7.00E-03	7.00E-02	7.00E-02	1.40E-01
[11]	Europe	Spain	5.28E-08	9.69E-04	2.61E-07	1.52E-11	3.38E-11	6.20E-07	1.67E-10	0.00E+00	6.20E-07	9.69E-04	9.69E-03	9.69E-03	1.94E-02
[13]	Europe	Spain	2.14E-07	3.93E-03	1.06E-06	6.18E-11	1.37E-10	2.51E-06	6.78E-10	0.00E+00	2.51E-06	3.93E-03	3.93E-02	3.93E-02	7.86E-02
[15]	Europe	Greece	6.75E-09	1.24E-04	3.34E-08	1.95E-12	4.32E-12	7.92E-08	2.14E-11	0.00E+00	7.92E-08	1.24E-04	1.24E-03	1.24E-03	2.48E-03
[15]	Europe	Greece	2.05E-08	3.77E-04	1.02E-07	5.93E-12	1.31E-11	2.41E-07	6.50E-11	0.00E+00	2.41E-07	3.77E-04	3.77E-03	3.77E-03	7.54E-03
[16]	Europe	Greece	1.19E-05	2.19E-01	5.90E-05	3.44E-09	7.62E-09	1.40E-04	3.77E-08	0.00E+00	1.40E-04	2.19E-01	2.19E+00	2.19E+00	4.37E+00
[17]	Europe	Finland	4.11E-08	7.53E-04	2.03E-07	1.19E-11	2.63E-11	4.82E-07	1.30E-10	0.00E+00	4.82E-07	7.54E-04	7.54E-03	7.54E-03	1.51E-02
[20]	Europe	Italy	2.94E-09	5.38E-05	1.45E-08	8.47E-13	1.88E-12	3.44E-08	9.29E-12	0.00E+00	3.44E-08	5.38E-05	5.38E-04	5.38E-04	1.08E-03
[25]	Europe	France	1.76E-07	3.22E-03	8.69E-07	5.06E-11	1.12E-10	2.06E-06	5.56E-10	0.00E+00	2.06E-06	3.22E-03	3.22E-02	3.22E-02	6.44E-02
[32]	Europe	UK	6.16E-08	1.13E-03	3.05E-07	1.78E-11	3.94E-11	7.23E-07	1.95E-10	0.00E+00	7.23E-07	1.13E-03	1.13E-02	1.13E-02	2.26E-02
[32]	Europe	Denmark	9.98E-08	1.83E-03	4.94E-07	2.88E-11	6.39E-11	1.17E-06	3.16E-10	0.00E+00	1.17E-06	1.83E-03	1.83E-02	1.83E-02	3.66E-02
[32]	Europe	Portugal	6.02E-07	1.10E-02	2.98E-06	1.74E-10	3.85E-10	7.06E-06	1.90E-09	0.00E+00	7.06E-06	1.10E-02	1.10E-01	1.10E-01	2.21E-01
[32]	Europe	Italy	5.28E-08	9.69E-04	2.61E-07	1.52E-11	3.38E-11	6.20E-07	1.67E-10	0.00E+00	6.20E-07	9.69E-04	9.69E-03	9.69E-03	1.94E-02
[32]	Europe	Greece	1.85E-07	3.39E-03	9.15E-07	5.33E-11	1.18E-10	2.17E-06	5.85E-10	0.00E+00	2.17E-06	3.39E-03	3.39E-02	3.39E-02	6.78E-02
[32]	Europe	Spain	2.79E-07	5.11E-03	1.38E-06	8.04E-11	1.78E-10	3.27E-06	8.83E-10	0.00E+00	3.27E-06	5.11E-03	5.11E-02	5.11E-02	1.02E-01
[32]	Europe	Hungary	1.67E-07	3.07E-03	8.28E-07	4.83E-11	1.07E-10	1.96E-06	5.30E-10	0.00E+00	1.96E-06	3.07E-03	3.07E-02	3.07E-02	6.14E-02
[32]	Europe	Poland	6.75E-08	1.24E-03	3.34E-07	1.95E-11	4.32E-11	7.92E-07	2.14E-10	0.00E+00	7.92E-07	1.24E-03	1.24E-02	1.24E-02	2.48E-02
[32]	Europe	Netherlands	1.73E-07	3.18E-03	8.57E-07	5.00E-11	1.11E-10	2.03E-06	5.48E-10	0.00E+00	2.03E-06	3.18E-03	3.18E-02	3.18E-02	6.35E-02
[32]	Europe	France	7.93E-08	1.45E-03	3.92E-07	2.29E-11	5.07E-11	9.30E-07	2.51E-10	0.00E+00	9.30E-07	1.45E-03	1.45E-02	1.45E-02	2.91E-02
[32]	Europe	Germany	7.05E-08	1.29E-03	3.49E-07	2.03E-11	4.51E-11	8.26E-07	2.23E-10	0.00E+00	8.27E-07	1.29E-03	1.29E-02	1.29E-02	2.58E-02
[34]	Europe	Germany	5.58E-08	1.02E-03	2.76E-07	1.61E-11	3.57E-11	6.54E-07	1.77E-10	0.00E+00	6.54E-07	1.02E-03	1.02E-02	1.02E-02	2.05E-02
[36]	Europe	Spain	2.03E-06	3.71E-02	1.00E-05	5.84E-10	1.30E-09	2.38E-05	6.41E-09	0.00E+00	2.38E-05	3.71E-02	3.71E-01	3.71E-01	7.43E-01
[37]	Europe	Romenia	1.35E-08	2.47E-04	6.67E-08	3.89E-12	8.62E-12	1.58E-07	4.27E-11	0.00E+00	1.58E-07	2.47E-04	2.47E-03	2.47E-03	4.94E-03
[21]	North America	USA	5.35E-07	1.05E-02	2.65E-06	1.55E-10	3.49E-10	6.87E-06	1.73E-09	0.00E+00	6.87E-06	1.06E-02	1.06E-01	1.06E-01	2.11E-01
[21]	North America	USA	9.83E-08	1.94E-03	4.87E-07	2.84E-11	6.41E-11	1.26E-06	3.17E-10	0.00E+00	1.26E-06	1.94E-03	1.94E-02	1.94E-02	3.88E-02
[21]	North America	USA	1.37E-08	2.69E-04	6.76E-08	3.95E-12	8.90E-12	1.75E-07	4.40E-11	0.00E+00	1.75E-07	2.69E-04	2.69E-03	2.69E-03	5.38E-03
[22]	North America	USA	8.33E-07	1.64E-02	4.12E-06	2.41E-10	5.43E-10	1.07E-05	2.69E-09	0.00E+00	1.07E-05	1.64E-02	1.64E-01	1.64E-01	3.28E-01
[31]	North America	Canada	2.73E-09	5.38E-05	1.35E-08	7.89E-13	1.78E-12	3.51E-08	8.80E-12	0.00E+00	3.51E-08	5.38E-05	5.38E-04	5.38E-04	1.08E-03
[35]	North America	USA	4.92E-09	9.69E-05	2.43E-08	1.42E-12	3.20E-12	6.31E-08	1.58E-11	0.00E+00	6.31E-08	9.69E-05	9.69E-04	9.69E-04	1.94E-03

Reference:	Continent:	Country:	<i>ADD_{soil}</i>	<i>ADD_{food}</i>	<i>ADD_{derm}</i>	<i>ADD_{inh}</i>	<i>Sfo</i> (soil)	<i>Sfo</i> (food)	<i>Sfo</i> (derm)	<i>IUR</i>	<i>ILCR</i>	<i>ADD_i</i>	<i>RfD_o</i>	<i>RfD_{obs}</i>	<i>HI</i>
[1]	South America	Argentina	7.60E-08	6.85E-04	3.76E-07	2.21E-11	4.81E-11	4.34E-07	2.38E-10	0.00E+00	4.34E-07	6.86E-04	6.86E-03	6.86E-03	1.37E-02
[1]	South America	Argentina	7.14E-08	6.44E-04	3.54E-07	2.08E-11	4.52E-11	4.07E-07	2.24E-10	0.00E+00	4.08E-07	6.44E-04	6.44E-03	6.44E-03	1.29E-02
[1]	South America	Argentina	9.90E-08	8.92E-04	4.90E-07	2.88E-11	6.27E-11	5.65E-07	3.10E-10	0.00E+00	5.65E-07	8.93E-04	8.93E-03	8.93E-03	1.79E-02
[2]	South America	Argentina	7.36E-10	6.63E-06	3.64E-09	2.14E-13	4.66E-13	4.20E-09	2.30E-12	0.00E+00	4.20E-09	6.63E-06	6.63E-05	6.63E-05	1.33E-04
[2]	South America	Argentina	2.91E-09	2.62E-05	1.44E-08	8.47E-13	1.84E-12	1.66E-08	9.12E-12	0.00E+00	1.66E-08	2.63E-05	2.63E-04	2.63E-04	5.25E-04
[2]	South America	Argentina	4.03E-08	3.63E-04	2.00E-07	1.17E-11	2.55E-11	2.30E-07	1.26E-10	0.00E+00	2.30E-07	3.63E-04	3.63E-03	3.63E-03	7.27E-03
[3]	South America	Argentina	4.61E-07	4.15E-03	2.28E-06	1.34E-10	2.92E-10	2.63E-06	1.44E-09	0.00E+00	2.63E-06	4.15E-03	4.15E-02	4.15E-02	8.31E-02
[4]	South America	Argentina	1.29E-07	1.16E-03	6.37E-07	3.74E-11	8.15E-11	7.34E-07	4.03E-10	0.00E+00	7.35E-07	1.16E-03	1.16E-02	1.16E-02	2.32E-02
[5]	South America	Argentina	3.89E-07	3.51E-03	1.93E-06	1.13E-10	2.46E-10	2.22E-06	1.22E-09	0.00E+00	2.22E-06	3.51E-03	3.51E-02	3.51E-02	7.02E-02
[7]	South America	Colombia	1.17E-06	1.06E-02	5.80E-06	3.41E-10	7.41E-10	6.68E-06	3.67E-09	0.00E+00	6.68E-06	1.06E-02	1.06E-01	1.06E-01	2.11E-01
[7]	South America	Argentina	2.05E-07	1.85E-03	1.02E-06	5.97E-11	1.30E-10	1.17E-06	6.43E-10	0.00E+00	1.17E-06	1.85E-03	1.85E-02	1.85E-02	3.70E-02
[9]	South America	Brazil	2.04E-05	1.83E-01	1.01E-04	5.92E-09	1.29E-08	1.16E-04	6.37E-08	0.00E+00	1.16E-04	1.83E-01	1.83E+00	1.83E+00	3.67E+00
[18]	South America	Argentina	4.05E-08	3.65E-04	2.00E-07	1.18E-11	2.56E-11	2.31E-07	1.27E-10	0.00E+00	2.31E-07	3.65E-04	3.65E-03	3.65E-03	7.30E-03
[23]	South America	Argentina	3.07E-09	2.76E-05	1.52E-08	8.91E-13	1.94E-12	1.75E-08	9.60E-12	0.00E+00	1.75E-08	2.76E-05	2.76E-04	2.76E-04	5.53E-04
[23]	South America	Argentina	3.07E-09	2.76E-05	1.52E-08	8.91E-13	1.94E-12	1.75E-08	9.60E-12	0.00E+00	1.75E-08	2.76E-05	2.76E-04	2.76E-04	5.53E-04
[23]	South America	Argentina	3.07E-09	2.76E-05	1.52E-08	8.91E-13	1.94E-12	1.75E-08	9.60E-12	0.00E+00	1.75E-08	2.76E-05	2.76E-04	2.76E-04	5.53E-04
[24]	South America	Argentina	3.75E-07	3.38E-03	1.86E-06	1.09E-10	2.38E-10	2.14E-06	1.18E-09	0.00E+00	2.14E-06	3.38E-03	3.38E-02	3.38E-02	6.77E-02
[26]	South America	Argentina	5.40E-08	4.86E-04	2.67E-07	1.57E-11	3.42E-11	3.08E-07	1.69E-10	0.00E+00	3.08E-07	4.87E-04	4.87E-03	4.87E-03	9.73E-03
[27]	South America	Argentina	7.51E-07	6.77E-03	3.72E-06	2.18E-10	4.75E-10	4.28E-06	2.35E-09	0.00E+00	4.29E-06	6.77E-03	6.77E-02	6.77E-02	1.35E-01
[28]	South America	Argentina	2.49E-06	2.24E-02	1.23E-05	7.22E-10	1.57E-09	1.42E-05	7.78E-09	0.00E+00	1.42E-05	2.24E-02	2.24E-01	2.24E-01	4.48E-01
[29]	South America	Argentina	4.72E-08	4.25E-04	2.34E-07	1.37E-11	2.99E-11	2.69E-07	1.48E-10	0.00E+00	2.69E-07	4.26E-04	4.26E-03	4.26E-03	8.51E-03
[30]	South America	Argentina	5.43E-08	4.89E-04	2.69E-07	1.58E-11	3.43E-11	3.09E-07	1.70E-10	0.00E+00	3.10E-07	4.89E-04	4.89E-03	4.89E-03	9.79E-03
[33]	South America	Argentina	1.89E-08	1.70E-04	9.36E-08	5.50E-12	1.20E-11	1.08E-07	5.92E-11	0.00E+00	1.08E-07	1.71E-04	1.71E-03	1.71E-03	3.41E-03

Table 8 summarises the Incremental Lifetime Cancer Risk (ILCR) and Hazard Index (HI) for AMPA, presenting the assessed values for each exposure routes (ADD_i): soil ingestion (ADD_{soil}), food ingestion (ADD_{food}), dermal contact (ADD_{derm}), and dust inhalation (ADD_{inh}); the correspondent slope factors (SF_i): oral slope factor (SF_{soil} and SF_{food}), dermal slope factor of dermal contact (SF_{abs}), and the inhalation unit risk (IUR), along with the reference dose for ingestion (RfD_o), and dermal contact (RfD_{abs}). The incremental lifetime carcinogenic risk (ILCR) and the non-cancer risk (hazard index - HI) are coloured according to the following parameters:

ILCR:

- Green cells indicate the risk to the human population to be acceptable ($ILCR < 1 \times 10^{-06}$),
- Yellow cells indicate some risk to the human population, with regulators being called to lower the risk with effective measures ($1 \times 10^{-06} < ILCR < 1 \times 10^{-4}$),
- Red cells indicate the high-risk probability of developing cancer over a lifetime ($ILCR > 1 \times 10^{-4}$).

HI:

- Green cells – considers that non-cancer health effects are not expected ($HI < 1$)
- Red cells – considers that non-cancer health effects are possible but not certain ($HI > 1$)

The equations and parameter ranges are presented in Section 2, which covers the experimental design, materials, and methods.

Table 8: ILCR and HI AMPA - Incremental lifetime carcinogenic risk (ILCR) and hazard index (HI) calculated for AMPA from different world regions (Asia, Europe, North and South America) for human health from the average daily dose by four exposure routes: soil intake, food intake, dermal contact, and inhalation. N.D.- denotes not determined.

Reference:	Continent:	Country:	<i>ADD_{soil}</i>	<i>ADD_{food}</i>	<i>ADD_{derm}</i>	<i>ADD_{inh}</i>	<i>Sfo (soil)</i>	<i>Sfo (food)</i>	<i>Sfo (derm)</i>	<i>IUR</i>	<i>ILCR</i>	<i>ADD_i</i>	<i>RfD_o</i>	<i>RfD_{obs}</i>	<i>HI</i>
[12]	Asia	Sri Lanka	2.73E-09	9.85E-05	1.35E-08	7.94E-13	1.68E-12	6.07E-08	8.32E-12	0.00E+00	6.07E-08	9.85E-05	9.85E-04	9.85E-04	1.97E-03
[14]	Asia	China	N.D.	N.D.	N.D.	N.D.	N.D.	N.D.	N.D.	N.D.	N.D.	N.D.	N.D.	N.D.	N.D.
[19]	Asia	Philippines	3.41E-09	1.23E-04	1.69E-08	9.93E-13	2.10E-12	7.59E-08	1.04E-11	0.00E+00	7.59E-08	1.23E-04	1.23E-03	1.23E-03	2.46E-03
[6]	Europe	Sweden	1.12E-07	2.40E-03	5.55E-07	3.23E-11	7.17E-11	1.53E-06	3.55E-10	0.00E+00	1.53E-06	2.40E-03	2.40E-02	2.40E-02	4.80E-02
[8]	Europe	Italy	2.76E-08	5.90E-04	1.37E-07	7.96E-12	1.77E-11	3.78E-07	8.73E-11	0.00E+00	3.78E-07	5.90E-04	5.90E-03	5.90E-03	1.18E-02
[10]	Europe	Czech	1.97E-08	4.21E-04	9.73E-08	5.67E-12	1.26E-11	2.69E-07	6.23E-11	0.00E+00	2.69E-07	4.21E-04	4.21E-03	4.21E-03	8.42E-03
[11]	Europe	Portugal	1.26E-06	2.70E-02	6.24E-06	3.64E-10	8.06E-10	1.72E-05	3.99E-09	0.00E+00	1.73E-05	2.70E-02	2.70E-01	2.70E-01	5.39E-01
[11]	Europe	Netherlands	1.55E-07	3.32E-03	7.67E-07	4.47E-11	9.92E-11	2.12E-06	4.91E-10	0.00E+00	2.12E-06	3.32E-03	3.32E-02	3.32E-02	6.63E-02
[11]	Europe	Spain	4.77E-07	1.02E-02	2.36E-06	1.38E-10	3.05E-10	6.53E-06	1.51E-09	0.00E+00	6.53E-06	1.02E-02	1.02E-01	1.02E-01	2.04E-01
[13]	Europe	Spain	1.65E-06	3.52E-02	8.15E-06	4.75E-10	1.05E-09	2.25E-05	5.21E-09	0.00E+00	2.25E-05	3.52E-02	3.52E-01	3.52E-01	7.05E-01
[15]	Europe	Greece	7.93E-09	1.70E-04	3.92E-08	2.29E-12	5.07E-12	1.08E-07	2.51E-11	0.00E+00	1.08E-07	1.70E-04	1.70E-03	1.70E-03	3.39E-03
[15]	Europe	Greece	4.99E-08	1.07E-03	2.47E-07	1.44E-11	3.19E-11	6.83E-07	1.58E-10	0.00E+00	6.83E-07	1.07E-03	1.07E-02	1.07E-02	2.14E-02
[16]	Europe	Greece	7.34E-07	1.57E-02	3.63E-06	2.12E-10	4.69E-10	1.00E-05	2.32E-09	0.00E+00	1.00E-05	1.57E-02	1.57E-01	1.57E-01	3.14E-01
[17]	Europe	Finland	3.52E-08	7.53E-04	1.74E-07	1.02E-11	2.25E-11	4.82E-07	1.12E-10	0.00E+00	4.82E-07	7.54E-04	7.54E-03	7.54E-03	1.51E-02
[20]	Europe	Italy	1.92E-08	4.11E-04	9.51E-08	5.55E-12	1.23E-11	2.63E-07	6.09E-11	0.00E+00	2.63E-07	4.11E-04	4.11E-03	4.11E-03	8.23E-03
[25]	Europe	France	3.96E-08	8.48E-04	1.96E-07	1.14E-11	2.54E-11	5.42E-07	1.25E-10	0.00E+00	5.42E-07	8.48E-04	8.48E-03	8.48E-03	1.70E-02
[32]	Europe	UK	1.73E-07	3.70E-03	8.57E-07	5.00E-11	1.11E-10	2.37E-06	5.48E-10	0.00E+00	2.37E-06	3.71E-03	3.71E-02	3.71E-02	7.41E-02
[32]	Europe	Denmark	1.79E-07	3.83E-03	8.86E-07	5.17E-11	1.15E-10	2.45E-06	5.67E-10	0.00E+00	2.45E-06	3.83E-03	3.83E-02	3.83E-02	7.66E-02
[32]	Europe	Portugal	5.64E-07	1.21E-02	2.79E-06	1.63E-10	3.61E-10	7.71E-06	1.78E-09	0.00E+00	7.71E-06	1.21E-02	1.21E-01	1.21E-01	2.41E-01
[32]	Europe	Italy	4.05E-07	8.66E-03	2.00E-06	1.17E-10	2.59E-10	5.54E-06	1.28E-09	0.00E+00	5.54E-06	8.67E-03	8.67E-02	8.67E-02	1.73E-01
[32]	Europe	Greece	1.12E-07	2.39E-03	5.52E-07	3.22E-11	7.14E-11	1.53E-06	3.53E-10	0.00E+00	1.53E-06	2.39E-03	2.39E-02	2.39E-02	4.77E-02
[32]	Europe	Spain	7.93E-08	1.70E-03	3.92E-07	2.29E-11	5.07E-11	1.08E-06	2.51E-10	0.00E+00	1.08E-06	1.70E-03	1.70E-02	1.70E-02	3.39E-02
[32]	Europe	Hungary	2.14E-07	4.58E-03	1.06E-06	6.18E-11	1.37E-10	2.93E-06	6.78E-10	0.00E+00	2.93E-06	4.58E-03	4.58E-02	4.58E-02	9.17E-02
[32]	Europe	Poland	1.23E-07	2.64E-03	6.10E-07	3.56E-11	7.89E-11	1.69E-06	3.90E-10	0.00E+00	1.69E-06	2.64E-03	2.64E-02	2.64E-02	5.28E-02
[32]	Europe	Netherlands	3.02E-07	6.47E-03	1.50E-06	8.72E-11	1.93E-10	4.14E-06	9.57E-10	0.00E+00	4.14E-06	6.47E-03	6.47E-02	6.47E-02	1.29E-01
[32]	Europe	France	2.29E-07	4.90E-03	1.13E-06	6.60E-11	1.46E-10	3.13E-06	7.25E-10	0.00E+00	3.13E-06	4.90E-03	4.90E-02	4.90E-02	9.80E-02
[32]	Europe	Germany	1.59E-07	3.39E-03	7.84E-07	4.57E-11	1.01E-10	2.17E-06	5.02E-10	0.00E+00	2.17E-06	3.39E-03	3.39E-02	3.39E-02	6.78E-02
[34]	Europe	Germany	4.99E-08	1.07E-03	2.47E-07	1.44E-11	3.19E-11	6.83E-07	1.58E-10	0.00E+00	6.83E-07	1.07E-03	1.07E-02	1.07E-02	2.14E-02
[36]	Europe	Spain	N.D.	N.D.	N.D.	N.D.	N.D.	N.D.	N.D.	N.D.	N.D.	N.D.	N.D.	N.D.	N.D.
[37]	Europe	Romenia	N.D.	N.D.	N.D.	N.D.	N.D.	N.D.	N.D.	N.D.	N.D.	N.D.	N.D.	N.D.	N.D.
[21]	North America	USA	1.64E-08	3.77E-04	8.11E-08	4.73E-12	1.07E-11	2.45E-07	5.28E-11	0.00E+00	2.45E-07	3.77E-04	3.77E-03	3.77E-03	7.54E-03
[21]	North America	USA	1.37E-08	3.14E-04	6.76E-08	3.95E-12	8.90E-12	2.04E-07	4.40E-11	0.00E+00	2.05E-07	3.14E-04	3.14E-03	3.14E-03	6.28E-03
[21]	North America	USA	1.37E-08	3.14E-04	6.76E-08	3.95E-12	8.90E-12	2.04E-07	4.40E-11	0.00E+00	2.05E-07	3.14E-04	3.14E-03	3.14E-03	6.28E-03
[22]	North America	USA	N.D.	N.D.	N.D.	N.D.	N.D.	N.D.	N.D.	N.D.	N.D.	N.D.	N.D.	N.D.	N.D.

Reference:	Continent:	Country:	<i>ADD_{soil}</i>	<i>ADD_{food}</i>	<i>ADD_{derm}</i>	<i>ADD_{inh}</i>	<i>Sfo (soil)</i>	<i>Sfo (food)</i>	<i>Sfo (derm)</i>	<i>IUR</i>	<i>ILCR</i>	<i>ADD_i</i>	<i>RfD_o</i>	<i>RfD_{obs}</i>	<i>HI</i>
[31]	North America	Canada	5.46E-08	1.26E-03	2.70E-07	1.58E-11	3.56E-11	8.18E-07	1.76E-10	0.00E+00	8.18E-07	1.26E-03	1.26E-02	1.26E-02	2.51E-02
[35]	North America	USA	3.01E-08	6.91E-04	1.49E-07	8.68E-12	1.96E-11	4.50E-07	9.68E-11	0.00E+00	4.50E-07	6.91E-04	6.91E-03	6.91E-03	1.38E-02
[1]	South America	Argentina	6.13E-10	6.45E-06	3.03E-09	1.78E-13	3.88E-13	4.08E-09	1.92E-12	0.00E+00	4.08E-09	6.45E-06	6.45E-05	6.45E-05	1.29E-04
[1]	South America	Argentina	2.24E-07	2.36E-03	1.11E-06	6.52E-11	1.42E-10	1.49E-06	7.03E-10	0.00E+00	1.49E-06	2.36E-03	2.36E-02	2.36E-02	4.72E-02
[1]	South America	Argentina	6.13E-10	6.45E-06	3.03E-09	1.78E-13	3.88E-13	4.08E-09	1.92E-12	0.00E+00	4.08E-09	6.45E-06	6.45E-05	6.45E-05	1.29E-04
[2]	South America	Argentina	1.93E-09	2.03E-05	9.56E-09	5.62E-13	1.22E-12	1.28E-08	6.05E-12	0.00E+00	1.29E-08	2.03E-05	2.03E-04	2.03E-04	4.06E-04
[2]	South America	Argentina	2.03E-08	2.13E-04	1.00E-07	5.90E-12	1.28E-11	1.35E-07	6.36E-11	0.00E+00	1.35E-07	2.13E-04	2.13E-03	2.13E-03	4.27E-03
[2]	South America	Argentina	2.16E-07	2.27E-03	1.07E-06	6.27E-11	1.37E-10	1.43E-06	6.75E-10	0.00E+00	1.44E-06	2.27E-03	2.27E-02	2.27E-02	4.54E-02
[3]	South America	Argentina	6.92E-07	7.27E-03	3.42E-06	2.01E-10	4.38E-10	4.60E-06	2.17E-09	0.00E+00	4.60E-06	7.27E-03	7.27E-02	7.27E-02	1.45E-01
[4]	South America	Argentina	5.21E-07	5.48E-03	2.58E-06	1.52E-10	3.30E-10	3.47E-06	1.63E-09	0.00E+00	3.47E-06	5.48E-03	5.48E-02	5.48E-02	1.10E-01
[5]	South America	Argentina	8.95E-07	9.41E-03	4.43E-06	2.60E-10	5.66E-10	5.95E-06	2.80E-09	0.00E+00	5.96E-06	9.41E-03	9.41E-02	9.41E-02	1.88E-01
[7]	South America	Colombia	6.35E-07	6.67E-03	3.14E-06	1.85E-10	4.02E-10	4.22E-06	1.99E-09	0.00E+00	4.22E-06	6.67E-03	6.67E-02	6.67E-02	1.33E-01
[7]	South America	Argentina	3.65E-07	3.84E-03	1.81E-06	1.06E-10	2.31E-10	2.43E-06	1.14E-09	0.00E+00	2.43E-06	3.84E-03	3.84E-02	3.84E-02	7.67E-02
[9]	South America	Brazil	7.98E-06	8.39E-02	3.95E-05	2.32E-09	5.05E-09	5.31E-05	2.50E-08	0.00E+00	5.31E-05	8.39E-02	8.39E-01	8.39E-01	1.68E+00
[18]	South America	Argentina	1.11E-07	1.17E-03	5.49E-07	3.22E-11	7.02E-11	7.38E-07	3.47E-10	0.00E+00	7.38E-07	1.17E-03	1.17E-02	1.17E-02	2.33E-02
[23]	South America	Argentina	9.83E-08	1.03E-03	4.86E-07	2.86E-11	6.22E-11	6.54E-07	3.08E-10	0.00E+00	6.54E-07	1.03E-03	1.03E-02	1.03E-02	2.07E-02
[23]	South America	Argentina	3.91E-08	4.11E-04	1.93E-07	1.14E-11	2.47E-11	2.60E-07	1.22E-10	0.00E+00	2.60E-07	4.11E-04	4.11E-03	4.11E-03	8.22E-03
[23]	South America	Argentina	4.93E-08	5.19E-04	2.44E-07	1.43E-11	3.12E-11	3.28E-07	1.54E-10	0.00E+00	3.28E-07	5.19E-04	5.19E-03	5.19E-03	1.04E-02
[24]	South America	Argentina	2.25E-06	2.37E-02	1.11E-05	6.55E-10	1.43E-09	1.50E-05	7.05E-09	0.00E+00	1.50E-05	2.37E-02	2.37E-01	2.37E-01	4.74E-01
[26]	South America	Argentina	2.18E-07	2.30E-03	1.08E-06	6.35E-11	1.38E-10	1.45E-06	6.84E-10	0.00E+00	1.45E-06	2.30E-03	2.30E-02	2.30E-02	4.60E-02
[27]	South America	Argentina	N.D.	N.D.	N.D.	N.D.	N.D.	N.D.	N.D.	N.D.	N.D.	N.D.	N.D.	N.D.	N.D.
[28]	South America	Argentina	1.19E-05	1.25E-01	5.91E-05	3.47E-09	7.56E-09	7.94E-05	3.74E-08	0.00E+00	7.95E-05	1.26E-01	1.26E+00	1.26E+00	2.51E+00
[29]	South America	Argentina	6.29E-07	6.61E-03	3.11E-06	1.83E-10	3.98E-10	4.18E-06	1.97E-09	0.00E+00	4.19E-06	6.62E-03	6.62E-02	6.62E-02	1.32E-01
[30]	South America	Argentina	4.55E-07	4.79E-03	2.25E-06	1.32E-10	2.88E-10	3.03E-06	1.43E-09	0.00E+00	3.03E-06	4.79E-03	4.79E-02	4.79E-02	9.58E-02
[33]	South America	Argentina	2.75E-07	2.89E-03	1.36E-06	7.99E-11	1.74E-10	1.83E-06	8.60E-10	0.00E+00	1.83E-06	2.89E-03	2.89E-02	2.89E-02	5.78E-02

2. Experimental design, materials and methods

The full details of the materials and methods are provided in Ferreira et al. [15]. This section briefly outlines the procedure for selecting relevant literature and the formulas used to calculate the ecological and human risk assessments.

2.1 Literature review

A comprehensive literature review was conducted as described in Ferreira et al. [15]. Relevant English, Portuguese, and Spanish records were obtained from Scopus and Google Scholar using targeted keywords. After removing duplicates, the records were screened in a step-wise manner. First, titles, abstracts, highlights, and keywords were reviewed. The remaining records were then evaluated against the following specific inclusion criteria: [list criteria 1-5].

Criterion 1: records must include the measurement of GLY and/or AMPA in field samples.

Criterion 2: records related to the study of Gly and/or AMPA degradation and other kinetic parameters that result from the direct contamination of field samples or studies that involve the direct contamination of soil in the field (e.g. micro- or mesocosms) are excluded.

Criterion 3: records that include the study of GLY and/or AMPA concentrations from field samples that accurately describe how samples were stored and preserved prior to analysis.

Criterion 4: Records must detail that the last application of GLY was made at least three months before the quantification.

Criterion 5: records with improperly described methodology, written in another language (e.g. record has a double abstract in English and Chinese), among others, were excluded.

Table 1 lists the 37 final manuscripts selected for this study.

2.2 Ecological Risk Assessment (ERA)

The Ecological Risk Assessment (ERA) is described by Ferreira et al. [15] and is based on the equations described by ECETOC [16], Peake et al. [17], and Pérez et al. [18] derived as follows (Eq. 1):

$$(Eq. 1) RQ = \frac{MEC}{PNEC}$$

RQ: risk quotient (toxicity unit),

MEC: measured environmental concentration (mg/kg soil),

PNEC: predicted no-effect environmental concentration (mg/kg soil).

The *PNEC* was derived as follows (Eq. 2):

$$(Eq. 2) PNEC = \frac{LC_{50}}{AF}$$

***LC*₅₀**: concentration that kills 50% of the sample population (mg/kg soil),

The *LC*₅₀ values used in this study are presented in Table 3. Since no toxicity data was available for AMPA, the *LC*₅₀ values of the parental compound (GLY) were multiplied by a value of 20x based on the AMPA/GLY ratio for *LC*₅₀ values of aquatic organisms described on the EFSA and ECOTOX databases. This is a conservative value, representing some uncertainty, as the toxicity of AMPA may not be 20x higher than the toxicity of GLY. Additionally, this conservative criterion would represent a worst-case scenario.

AF: assessment factor (*AF* = 50, without a unit of measure), applied to reduce uncertainties about the accuracy, model errors, lack of toxicity data, and inherent variability between laboratory exposure and field conditions as described by Vašíčková et al. [19].

The RQ is presented in Table 4 and Table 5, and was classified as low ecological risk (RQ < 0.1), moderate ecological risk (0.1 < RQ < 1.0), and high ecological risk (RQ > 1.0), according to Pérez et al. [18].

2.3 Human Risk Assessment (HRA)

The Human Risk Assessment (HRA) is described by Ferreira et al. [15] and was developed according to the Exposure Factors Handbook [5] and Generic Exposure Routes Assumptions document [20]. The HRA was estimated from generic characteristics of adults. Details of the human lifestyle, physiological and behavioural parameters are presented in Table 6.

A probabilistic risk model was used to estimate carcinogenic incidence based on the average daily dose by *i* exposure routes [*ADD*_{*i*} – mg/(kg/day)], expressed in Eq. 3 to Eq. 6, and being:

***ADD*_{soil}**: the soil ingestion route,

***ADD*_{food}**: the food ingestion route,

***ADD*_{derm}**: the dermal contact route,

***ADD*_{inh}**: the dust inhalation route.

$$(Eq. 3) ADD_{soil} = \frac{C_{soil} \times IR_{soil} \times ED \times EF \times CF}{BW \times AT}$$

$$(Eq. 4) ADD_{food} = \frac{C_{soil} \times BCF \times IR_{veget} \times ED \times EF}{BW \times AT}$$

$$(Eq. 5) ADD_{derm} = \frac{C_{soil} \times SA \times DAF \times ABS \times ED \times EF \times CF}{BW \times AT}$$

$$(Eq. 6) ADD_{inh} = \frac{C_{soil} \times IR_{air} \times ED \times EF}{PEF \times BW \times AT}$$

C_{soil}: concentration of the pollutant on soil (mg/kg soil);

IR_{soil}: represents the daily soil ingest rate (mg/day);

ED: is the exposure duration (year);

EF: is the exposure frequency (day/year);

CF: is the conversion factor (kg/mg);

BW: is the bodyweight of the individual adult (kg);

AT: is the average lifespan of an adult (day);

BCF: is the bioconcentration factor (without a unit of measure);

IR_{veget}: is the daily vegetable ingestion rate (kg/day); **SA** is the surface area of the skin that contact with the soil (cm²/day);

DAF: is the soil dermal adhesion factor (mg/cm²);

ABS: is the dermal absorption factor (without a unit of measure);

IR_{air}: is the air inhalation rate (m³/day); and

PEF: is the particle emission factor (m³/kg).

The incremental lifetime carcinogenic risk (*ILCR*) was calculated using the estimated *ADD_i* multiplied by the *SF_i* as follows (Eq. 7):

$$(Eq. 7) \quad ILCR = \sum(ADD_i \times SF_i)$$

SF_i: is a carcinogenic slope factor that was added to the equations to define the upper confidence limit on the increased risk from *i* exposure route. The *SF_i* includes the oral slope factor [*SF_o*, – mg/(kg/day)], dermal slope factor of dermal contact [*SF_{abs}*, – mg/(kg/day)], and the inhalation unit risk (*IUR* – mg/m³).

Details of the parameters used to estimate the risk to human health are available in Table 6. The *ILCR* < 1 x 10⁻⁶ considers the risk to the human population to be acceptable, while *ILCR* > 1 x 10⁻⁴ indicates the high probability of risk over a lifetime. The non-cancer risk (hazard index - *HI*) was estimated using equation 8 (Eq. 8):

$$(Eq. 8) \quad HI = \sum \frac{ADD_i}{SF_i}$$

RfD [**RfD_i – mg/(kg/day)**] is defined as the daily maximum permissible values for the GLY or AMPA of the two (*i*) exposure pathways, including reference dose for ingestion (*RfD_o*), and dermal contact (*RfD_{abs}* = *RfD_o* x *ABS_{GI}*). *ABS_{GI}* is the fraction of GLY or AMPA absorbed in the gastrointestinal tract. The daily maximum reference dose for the inhalation exposure pathway could not be calculated due to the properties of GLY and AMPA (e.g. polarity and octanol-water partition coefficient), resulting in very low vapour pressure and low volatility. An *HI* lower than unity (*HI* < 1) reflects a no non-cancer risk.

3. Ethics statements

The data used in this study has been published previously and is available to the scientific community.

4. CRediT author statement

Nuno G. C. Ferreira: investigation, conceptualisation, validation, resources, supervision, formal analysis, funding acquisition and project administration. **Karlo Alves da Silva:** investigation, formal analysis and data curation. **Ana T. B. Guimarães:** conceptualisation, validation and data curation. **Cíntia Mara Ribas de Oliveira:** conceptualisation, validation, resources, supervision, funding acquisition and project administration. All authors contributed to the writing and editing the initial and final manuscript.

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4. Declaration of interests

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

5. References (Do not include the 37 based manuscripts)

- [1] A.I. Mohamed, G.A. Nair, H.H. Kassem, M. Nuruzzaman, Impact of pesticides on the survival and body mass of the earthworm *Aporrectodea caliginosa* (Annelida: Oligochaeta), *Acta Zool. Fenn.* (1995) 344–347.
- [2] Y. Wang, S. Wu, L. Chen, C. Wu, R. Yu, Q. Wang, X. Zhao, Toxicity assessment of 45 pesticides to the epigeic earthworm *Eisenia fetida*, *Chemosphere.* 88 (2012) 484–491. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.CHEMOSPHERE.2012.02.086>.

- [3] L. Piola, J. Fuchs, M.L. Oneto, S. Basack, E. Kesten, N. Casabé, Comparative toxicity of two glyphosate-based formulations to *Eisenia andrei* under laboratory conditions, *Chemosphere*. 91 (2013) 545–551. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemosphere.2012.12.036>.
- [4] M.J.G. Santos, M.F.L. Ferreira, A. Cachada, A.C. Duarte, J.P. Sousa, Pesticide application to agricultural fields: Effects on the reproduction and avoidance behaviour of *Folsomia candida* and *Eisenia andrei*, *Ecotoxicology*. 21 (2012) 2113–2122. <https://doi.org/10.1007/S10646-012-0963-7/TABLES/4>.
- [5] EPA, Environmental Protection Agency - Exposure Factors Handbook, EPA-600-R-090-052F. (2011). www.epa.gov.
- [6] WorldData, Life Expectancy, (2020). <https://www.worlddata.info/life-expectancy.php#:~:text=The world average age of,data from the year 2020%0A> (accessed April 5, 2023).
- [7] C. Qu, S. Albanese, J. Li, D. Cicchella, D. Zuzolo, D. Hope, P. Cerino, A. Pizzolante, A.L. Doherty, A. Lima, B. De Vivo, Organochlorine pesticides in the soils from Benevento provincial territory, southern Italy: Spatial distribution, air-soil exchange, and implications for environmental health, *Sci. Total Environ*. 674 (2019) 159–170. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2019.04.029>.
- [8] WorldData, Average height and weight by country, (2019). <https://www.worlddata.info/average-bodyheight.php> (accessed April 5, 2023).
- [9] EPA, CompTox Chemicals Dashboard v2.2, (2022). <https://comptox.epa.gov/dashboard/chemical/env-fate-transport/DTXSID1024122?deepLink=26%0A> (accessed April 5, 2023).
- [10] EPA, CompTox Chemicals Dashboard v2.2, (2023). <https://comptox.epa.gov/dashboard/chemical/env-fate-transport/DTXSID1024122?deepLink=26%0A> (accessed April 5, 2023).
- [11] FAO, Food Available and Consumption - FAOSTAT, (2023). <http://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data> (accessed April 5, 2023).
- [12] ORS, Office of Research and Standards, Weighted Skin-Soil Adherence Factors, in: *Guid. Dispos. Site Risk Charact. – Support Massachusetts Conting. Plan, 2002*: pp. 1–17. <https://www.mass.gov/doc/technical-update-weighted-skin-soil-adherence-factors-0/download#:~:text=The skin-soil adherence factor,or hazardous material in soil>.
- [13] OEHHA, California Office of Environmental Health Hazard Assessment. Glyphosate to be Listed under Proposition 65 as Known to the State to Cause Cancer, 2017. (2017). <https://oehha.ca.gov/proposition-65/cnr/glyphosate-be-listed-under-proposition-65-known-state-cause-cancer>.
- [14] ATSDR, Agency for Toxicity Substances and Disease Registry, (2019). <https://www.atsdr.cdc.gov/toxprofiles/tp214-c5.pdf> (accessed October 15, 2019).
- [15] Ferreira NGC, Alves da Silva K, Tereza Bittencourt Guimarães A, Mara Ribas de Oliveira C. Hotspots of soil pollution: possible glyphosate and aminomethylphosphonic acid risks on terrestrial ecosystems and human health. *Environ Int*. 2023:108135.
- [16] ECETOC, Soil and Sediment Risk Assessment of Organic Chemicals, European Centre for Ecotoxicology and Toxicology of Chemicals, 2004. <https://www.ecetoc.org/wp-content/uploads/2014/08/ECETOC-TR-092.pdf>.

- [17] B.M. Peake, R. Braund, A.Y.C. Tong, L.A. Tremblay, *Impact of pharmaceuticals on the environment*, Elsevier Ltd., 2016. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-1-907568-25-1.00005-0>.
- [18] D.J. Pérez, F.G. Iturburu, G. Calderon, L.A.E. Oyesqui, E. De Gerónimo, V.C. Aparicio, Ecological risk assessment of current-use pesticides and biocides in soils, sediments and surface water of a mixed land-use basin of the Pampas region, Argentina, *Chemosphere*. 263 (2021) 1–14. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemosphere.2020.128061>.
- [19] J. Vašíčková, M. Hvězdová, P. Kosubová, J. Hofman, Ecological risk assessment of pesticide residues in arable soils of the Czech Republic, *Chemosphere*. 216 (2019) 479–487. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemosphere.2018.10.158>.
- [20] Michigan, Department of Environmental Quality. White Paper : Generic Exposure Pathway Assumptions and Data Sources, Lansing, 2014. https://www.michigan.gov/documents/deq/deq-rrd-TAG4-WhitePaper2GenericExposureAssumptionsFinalDraft5-28-14_472094_7.pdf.